

Research Article

**BISPECTRAL INDEX GUIDED ANAESTHESIA FOR
OFF-PUMP CORONARY
ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING: THE WAY FORWARD
FOR A CRIPPLED HEART**Sanjeev Singh^{1,2,3}, Anbarasu Annamalai^{3,4}¹Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana²Directorate of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital, Kumasi, Ghana³Department of Cardiac Anaesthesia, NHIMS, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.⁴National Heart Centre, Royal Hospital, Muscat, Oman***Corresponding author**

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**Abstract
Background**

Bispectral index (BIS) monitoring reduces the utilisation of anaesthetic agents during general anaesthesia during surgery. This study was designed to test whether the use of BIS monitoring reduces the anaesthetic requirements during off-pump (OP) coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) and its effect on the clinical outcome.

Materials and methods

This was a clinical, prospective, and randomised study conducted after ethical approval. 60 adult patients undergoing elective OP-CABG were the subjects for this study. Patients received either isoflurane or propofol anaesthesia. BIS monitoring, which guided the dose of the anaesthetic agent, BIS value maintained at 50. The amount of anaesthetic agent (isoflurane or propofol) administered from the start of anaesthesia to the end of the surgical procedure was calculated and were compared in four groups of patients. Group I (No BIS-I) received isoflurane; end-tidal concentration was maintained at 1-1.2 % in a low flow technique throughout the procedure, Group II (BIS-I) received isoflurane in a low flow technique; inspired concentration was dictated by BIS value maintained at 50, Group III (No BIS-P) received propofol at a dose range of 4-8 mg/kg/hr and Group IV (BIS-P) the propofol infusion rate was dictated by BIS value maintained at 50.

Results

The quantities of isoflurane for Group-II as compare to Group-I (4 ± 3.65 and 7 ± 4.62 ml/hr) and propofol for Group-IV as compare to Group-III (24 ± 5.94 and 36 ± 7.52 ml/hr) were significantly less. Length of intubation was significantly less for Group-II and Group-IV as 1.7 ± 1.63 and 1.9 ± 1.74 hrs respectively. The requirement of inotropes was significantly less for Group-II (16.4 ± 5.43) hrs.

Conclusions

BIS-guided anaesthesia reduces the anaesthetic agent required for the performance of OP-CABG. This can be extrapolated in terms of saving anaesthetic agents, reduced need for inotropes/vasoactive agents, and faster recovery.

Key words: Bispectral index, isoflurane, off-pump coronary artery bypass grafting, propofol

Introduction

The recent trend of fast track early tracheal extubation after surgery has been seen in cardiac anaesthesia facilitates [1-3]. The safety of this early extubation practice in cardiac surgical patients has been extensively reported in the last few years [4]. Fast-track protocols depend on a low-dose-opioid with other anaesthetic to expedite recovery of spontaneous respiration, extubation, and ambulation [5]. Fast-tracking is fuelled partly by Human resources and marketing forces demanding more cost-effective quality care by decreased hospital costs through reduced intensive care unit and hospital stay [6].

The measurement of the depth of anaesthesia is of clinical interest for titrating anaesthetic drugs and for avoiding patient awareness during surgery. However, defining “anaesthetic depth” is difficult as unresponsiveness cannot be measured directly and there is no clear definition of what “depth of anaesthesia during surgery” means exactly [7]. In the last decade, there have been several variables, such as response to the loss of consciousness, skin incision, or drug concentrations, which have been represented by different parameters, such as haemodynamics [8, 9], pupillary reflex [10], skin conductivity [11] and oesophageal contractility [12] to assess the

depth of anaesthesia. The most reliable variables were derived from the electroencephalogram (EEG). The bispectral index (BIS), a modern variable derived from the phase coupling of the spontaneous EEG [13], has been investigated in different studies. High correlation coefficients between BIS and propofol plasma concentrations and clinical criteria of sedation have been observed. It has been shown that BIS-monitored anaesthesia reduced the risk of awareness in 'at risk' adult surgical patients [14]. Cardiac surgical patients have incidences of intra-operative awareness. BIS monitoring reduces the incidence of awareness during general anaesthesia requiring endotracheal intubation and muscle relaxants for surgery [15].

The current study was aimed to test the reliability of BIS during the conduct of OP-CABG, to find out if BIS monitoring alters the dose of anaesthetic agents and their effect on the clinical outcome.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was undertaken after obtaining institutional ethical approval by the Committee on Human Research Publications and Ethics (CHRPE). Informed consent was obtained from 60 patients. The study population consisted of ASA physical status III, male and female adults between the ages of 35-70 years scheduled for elective OPCABG surgical procedures under general anaesthesia.

Study Design

This study was a prospective, randomised, and double-blinded clinical comparison study. The Sample size for the study was 60 generated using a sample size calculator. The study participants were randomly divided into four groups by a computer-generated randomisation table. Person A involved in the randomisation process, Person B prepared the study drug, whilst Person C was responsible for the patient's intraoperative and Intensive Care Unit (ICU) records. Person A, C, and the patient were kept unaware of the study drugs to enable double-blinding.

Inclusion Criteria

The study was conducted in adult patients of both genders, age ≤ 60 years, belonging to ASA Grade III undergoing elective OPCABG surgery with general anaesthesia.

Exclusion Criteria

Exclusion criteria for the study included patients who were >60 years of age, poor left ventricular (LV) function, ejection fraction (LVEF) $< 40\%$, undergoing emergency surgery, BMI >40 , patients requiring extracorporeal circulation either electively or during the course of the operation, LV aneurysms, renal/hepatic dysfunction, patients requiring preoperative or intraoperative Intra-aortic balloon pump (IABP) and unstable angina, carotid stenosis, cerebrovascular accident (CVA), excessive alcohol intake and drug abuse.

Preoperative Preparation

The day prior to surgery all patients underwent a pre-anaesthetic evaluation with special consideration to elicit any new complication as well as previous anaesthetic history and drug sensitivity. All preoperative routine investigations rechecked. All procedures were explained to the patients and they received tablet diazepam 10mg the night before surgery in an attempt to alleviate the anxiety of the patients. All patients were advised to continue antihypertensive and anti-anginal medications as per prescription in the night and morning of surgery with few sips of water. Patients were fasted the night prior to surgery.

Anaesthetic Protocol

After patient identification, a short preoperative history was taken, clinical examination and routine investigations were rechecked in all patients. After arrival to the operating room, oxygen saturation in 4 limbs was checked without oxygen then patients were administered O₂ and monitoring of

ECG (5 lead) with automated ST-segment analysis (Marquette Solar 5000, GE Medical System, Milwaukee, USA) and pulse oximetry were initiated. A 14-G intravenous cannula was inserted in the dorsum of the right hand and an 18-G, 9 cm intra-arterial cannula was introduced into the right femoral artery for monitoring of the arterial pressure and obtaining arterial blood for analysis. Anaesthesia was induced, while patients breathed 100% oxygen by facemask, using a combination of fentanyl 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, Midazolam 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and sleep dose of thiopentone. Endotracheal intubation was performed after administration of pancuronium bromide 0.15 mg/kg. Patients were mechanically ventilated using the low-flow technique (fresh gas flow of 1 L/min) using anaesthesia machine (Excel 210 SE, Dattex Ohmeda, Madison, MI, USA) to achieve end-tidal carbon-dioxide tensions of 35 ± 3 mm. Inspired and expired gas concentration of O₂, CO₂ & isoflurane was measured using a smart anaesthetic gas monitoring system (Smart anaesthesia multi-gas module, Solar 5000, GE Medical Systems, Milwaukee, USA). Haemodynamic parameters were maintained within 20% of the basal values with dopamine, phenylephrine, adrenaline, nor-adrenaline, nitroglycerine, sodium nitroprusside as required. To maintain the patient's temperature at normothermia Bear Hugger warming unit, warming blanket and warm intravenous fluids were used. Filling pressures and fluid balance were maintained using Ringers lactate solution & 6% hydroxyethyl starch (HAES-steril, Fresenius Kabi). The total amount of fentanyl and midazolam administered during the entire procedure was restricted to 500 μg and 10 mg respectively. Intraoperative and postoperative analgesia was supplemented with the use of rectal diclofenac sodium administered after anaesthetic induction in the operating room.

BIS is a processed electroencephalogram (EEG) with advanced algorithms that report a number from 0 to 100. As awake 100 and 0 represents complete EEG inactivity. Patients were randomly divided into four groups by computer-generated randomisation table as follows: Group I (No BIS-I): In this group, anaesthesia was maintained using isoflurane in oxygen; the end-tidal concentration of isoflurane was adjusted to 1 – 1.2 % during the entire procedure. Group II (BIS-I): In this group, anaesthesia was maintained using isoflurane in oxygen: the isoflurane inspired concentration was adjusted to derive a BIS value of 50 ± 5 . Group III (No BIS-P): In this group, anaesthesia was maintained with propofol 50mg bolus then infusion at 6–8 mg/kg/hr till sternotomy and 4–6 mg/kg/hr thereafter. Group IV (BIS-P): In this group, anaesthesia with propofol 50mg bolus then maintained with variable propofol infusion rate, titrated to a BIS value of 50 ± 5 . In Group II (BIS-I) & Group IV (BIS-P) monitoring included BIS: in these patients before induction of general anaesthesia, noninvasive monitoring device the BIS monitor (Model A-2000, Aspect Medical Systems, Inc, Natick, MA, USA) was applied. The 2-channel electroencephalographic signal for the BIS was captured using cutaneous electrodes (Zipprep, Aspect Medical Systems, Natick, MA, USA) positioned over the outer malar bones, midline on the forehead, and adjacent to the centre electrode. A smoothing window of 15-second duration, which updates every 2 seconds was used, the impedance was maintained less than 5 k Ω . To minimise artifactual error, the BIS score was recorded exclusively in the absence of possible confounding signals.

Isoflurane was administered in groups I (No BIS-I) and II (BIS-I) through a calibrated Isotec 5 vaporiser (Ohmeda BOC Health care, west Yorkshire, UK). Propofol was infused in groups III (No BIS-P) and IV (BIS-P) using a syringe pump (Perfusor Compact, B Braun, Melsungen AG) 50 ml syringe ml (Becton Dickinson, Singapore). In groups I (No BIS-I) and II (BIS-I) the amount of isoflurane utilised during the procedure was calculated by using the formula: consumption of the anaesthetic agent in ml/h = 3 x set concentration % x fresh gas flow L/min [16, 17].

Surgical Protocol

All patients had the CABG done after a median sternotomy under normothermic conditions. Traditional cardiopulmonary bypass circuit was kept ready as a rescue measure. Patients received heparin in a dose of 300 units/kg before anastomosis to maintain an activated coagulation time of greater than 300 seconds. The proximal anastomosis was done with partial clamping of the ascending aorta, and the distal grafting was performed using the octopus II tissue stabiliser. OP-CABG was converted to conventional CABG with CPB at any point should the patient not tolerate the period of ischaemia required to complete the graft or for surgical reasons. ST-segment analysis was carried out during the entire procedure and leads I, II, and V5 were continuously monitored. ST-segment depression or elevation of >1.0mm was considered clinically significant. All patients were ventilated postoperatively for 2-3 hours and tracheal extubation performed after satisfying the criteria for extubation (namely, the patient is conscious, warm, not bleeding excessively, and fully recovered from the effects of neuromuscular blocking agents).

Intensive care unit Protocol

An intensive care unit research fellow interviewed all patients once at 18 hrs after extubation. After an initial introduction, a very structured interview was begun. Each patient was asked the following standard set of questions. 1. What remains the last thing you remember before surgery? 2. What was the very next thing you remember? 3. Can you recall anything in between these two periods? 4. Did you have any dreams during your operation? If the patient indicated that he or she did not have an explicit memory of intraoperative events while answering these questions, no further questions were asked. If the patient indicated that he or she had an explicit memory of intraoperative events while answering the questions, the following sub-questions were asked: 1. What did you notice; sounds, touch, pain, paralysis? 2. How long did it last? 3. Did you try to alert anything? 4. Have there been any consequences for you? No supplemental questions were asked. Awareness was defined by the presence of an explicit memory of any event from induction of anaesthesia to recovery of consciousness in the cardiac surgical Intensive Care Unit (ICU). If the patient gave a history of awareness, he/she was visited by the senior author and the attending anaesthesiologist to discuss and explain the peri-operative events.

Parameters and Statistical Analysis

Summary statistics of patient gender, age, weight, height, and body mass

Table 1: Distribution of patient's demographic profile

Parameters (mean ± SD)	Group I (n=15)	Group II (n=15)	Group III (n=15)	Group IV (n=15)	p-Value
Age (Years)	51.78±12.73	50.80±13.21	51.98±13.82	51.26±13.21	0.841
Weight (Kg)	82.76±8.52	81.62±8.17	80.93±8.36	81.29±7.41	0.342
Height (cm)	155.32±5.75	156.25±5.41	157.70± 6.10	155.83±5.32	0.575
BMI(Kg/m ²)	34.3±0.92	33.4±0.72	32.50±0.51	33.6±0.67	0.439
Sex M:F percent	2:1 (66.7%:33.3%)	1.5:1 (60%:40%)	2.75:1 (73.3%:26.7%)	1.5:1 (60%:40%)	0.138

Data are presented as means ± standard deviation, ratio and percentages. Yrs = Years, Kg = Kilogram, Cm = Centimetre, M = Male, F = Female, p-value is significant* <0.05.

index (BMI) for all four groups were reported as means ± standard deviation (SD). Patients clinical variables, anaesthetic agents used, the amount of propofol calculated in ml/hr, and isoflurane administered during the procedure was calculated by using the formula: consumption of anaesthetic agent in ml/hr = 3 x set concentration % x fresh gas flow L/min [13].

ANOVA with repeated measures was used to compare the changes in haemodynamic variables. Analyzed data were presented in the form of mean, where the level of significance was given as p-value in a separate column. A p-value of less than 0.05 was taken as significant. Man-Whitney U test was used to analyse the data since the data were not following a normal distribution. Nominal data were compared using the Chi-Square test. The statistical package SPSS 14.0 was used

RESULTS

Sixty patients were included in this study. The demographic and preoperative characteristics of each group as shown in tables 1-2. The four groups were comparable concerning the demographic and preoperative data (p<0.05).

The quantity of isoflurane required for the OP-CABG was 43 ± 13.17 ml in Group I (No BIS-I) and 24±12.42 ml in-Group II (BIS-I) and showed a 44.2% reduction in requirement of isoflurane with BIS monitoring, which was statistically significant. The quantity of propofol required for the conduct of OP-CABG was 176±9.63 ml in-group III (No BIS-P) and 120 ±6.75 ml in-group IV (BIS-P) also showed a 31.8% reduction in propofol usage. The reduction in propofol requirements with BIS monitoring was also statistically significant (Table-III).

All patients tolerated the OP-CABG well, and none was converted to an open-heart procedure. Time to awaken and extubation was significantly reduced in-group II (BIS-I), and IV (BIS-P) as compared to group I (No BIS-I) & III (No BIS-P). Inotropes needed in group II (BIS-I) significantly less as compared to group I (No BIS-I), III (No BIS-P), and IV (BIS-P). There were no significant differences between the duration of surgery, intensive care unit (ICU) stay, and length of hospital stay in the four groups. No patient had explicit memory of any event from the induction of anaesthetic to the recovery of consciousness in the cardiac surgical ICU.

Table 2: Distribution of patient's preoperative characteristics

Clinical Variables	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV	p-value
Number of grafts (mean)	2.6	2.8	3.0	2.7	0.621
LV Ejection Fraction (mean)	49	50	47	48	0.763
Co-morbid conditions Hypertension (mean)	7	8	7	6	0.524
Diabetes mellitus (mean)	5	6	6	5	0.732
Previous MI (mean)	6	7	5	7	0.637
Preoperative medications β-blockers (mean)	14	15	15	14	0.852
Calcium channel blockers (mean)					
Diuretics (mean)	7	6	7	8	0.531
	-	-	-	-	-
Digoxin (mean)	-	-	-	-	-
ACEI (mean)	5	6	5	6	0.632

Data are presented as means and p-value. ANOVA with repeated measures was used to compare the clinical variables. p-value is significant <0.05. ACEI= angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors; LV=left ventricular; MI=myocardial infarction.

Table 3: Comparison of the quantity of anaesthetic agents used in different study groups

Anaesthetic Agents Used	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
Total quantity of Isoflurane (mean ± SD) ml	43 ± 13.17	24 ± 12.42 *	-	-
Isoflurane ml/hr (mean ± SD)	7 ± 4.62	4 ± 3.65 *	-	-
Total quantity of propofol (mean ± SD) ml	-	-	176 ± 9.63	120 ± 6.75 *
Propofol ml/hr (mean ± SD)	-	-	36 ± 7.52	24 ± 5.94 *

Data are presented as means ± SD, and p-value compared to group I & II and III & IV. p-value significant* <0.05.

Table 4: Distribution of patient's postoperative characteristics

Clinical Variables	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
Duration of surgery (hrs)	4.5 ± 1.9	4.6 ± 1.3	5.3 ± 1.7	4.7 ± 1.8
Length of intubation (hrs)	5.5 ± 2.64	2.4 ± 1.63*	5.1 ± 1.41	2.1 ± 1.74*
Length of ICU stay (days)	1.6 ± 4.96	1.5 ± 4.63	1.4 ± 4.83	1.4 ± 5.44
Length of hospital stay (days)	7 ± 1.94	6 ± 1.73	7 ± 1.38	7 ± 1.94

Intergroup p-value compared group I&II and III & IV. ICU= Intensive Care unit, p-value significant* <0.05.

Table 5: Comparison of inotropic drugs used in all groups

Variable	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
Phenylephrine / Adrenaline / Noradrenaline / Dopamine	29.6 ± 5.27 hrs	16.4 ± 5.43 hrs*	28.7 ± 5.16 hrs	25.3 ± 5.37 hrs

Nitroglycerine/ Sodium nitroprusside	6.4±2.41 hrs	5.9±2.83 hrs	6.8±2.37 hrs	6.7±2.31 Hrs
No Inotrope infusion	2%	5%	1%	3%
1-Inotrope infusion	45%	43%	57%	51%
2 or more inotropes infusion	53%	52%	42%	46%

Data are presented as means ± standard deviation (SD), and percentage, hrs= Hours, p-value significant* <0.05.

DISCUSSION

During surgery under general anaesthesia, the anaesthetist keep on adjusting the amount of anaesthetic drugs, to ensure that the patient remains unconscious. These adjustments were made according to clinical signs, such as the patient's heart rate or blood pressure or respiratory rate or end-tidal anaesthetic gas (ETAG) for anaesthesia that is given [18]. However, using these methods alone may increase the chance that the patient is given too little or too much anaesthetic. Intraoperative awareness, a distressing event in which a patient may become conscious enough to recall events during surgery, is very rare and may be caused by too little anaesthetic. Too much anaesthetic may lead to a longer time needed to reach full recovery and myocardial depression especially in patients with poor heart function. Until recently, there was no practical way to establish if a patient had been rendered in an anaesthetic state where memory and recall were prevented. Although several new monitors are under study, the BIS monitor (Bi-spectral Index) has undergone extensive investigation and is presently approved for use. Many authors have demonstrated a good correlation between BIS index and level of awareness [19-21]. A BIS index of 55 is associated with a low likelihood of intraoperative awareness without producing a very deep level of general anaesthesia [22]. While comparing the abilities of narcotrend (NT) and BIS to monitor the depth of anaesthesia, NT and BIS were found to be more reliable indicators for the assessment of anaesthetic states of a patient than the classical electroencephalographic variables and haemodynamics [23, 24]. In a study with continuous infusion of fentanyl and midazolam anaesthesia for cardiac surgery, a BIS of 50 was effective in preventing intraoperative awareness [25]. In our study BIS index was used to maintain a constant, moderate depth of anaesthesia and the anaesthesia dose was adjusted to obtain a BIS value of 50. This demonstrated a reduction of 44.2% isoflurane and 31.8% propofol requirements during the OP-CABG with BIS at 50. Our findings were similar to Song et al as they showed titrating desflurane and sevoflurane using BIS monitor decreased the utilisation of these volatile anaesthetic agents and contributed to a faster emergence from anaesthesia in outpatients undergoing laparoscopic tubal ligation procedures [26]. Likewise, Gajraj et al study showed titrating propofol with BIS monitoring decreases requirements and significantly improves recovery [27].

Vretzakis et al. in their study evaluated the influence of BIS on decision-making. BIS monitoring was useful in taking corrective measures like titration of anaesthetic drugs in 70.5% of patients, and titration of vasoactive drugs in 8% [28]. In our study, BIS significantly reduced the requirement of anaesthetic agents isoflurane and propofol, inotrope infusion, and length of intubation similar to other studies [27, 28]. BIS enables one to titrate anaesthesia to meet individual patient's needs for example those with haemodynamic instability, cardiovascular disease, and elderly subjects.

In a study, Gan et al demonstrated a reduced use of propofol and faster recovery compared with standard clinical practice and this may result in potential economic benefits [29]. The length of postoperative intubation with mechanical ventilation postoperatively was significantly less in group II (BIS-I), and IV (BIS-P). In group II isoflurane requirements were 44%

less when compared to group I and in the group, IV propofol requirement was 32% less when compared to group III. The recovery profile of propofol is better than that of isoflurane 5.1 ± 1.41 and 5.5 ± 2.64 hrs without BIS and 2.1 ± 1.74 and 2.4 ± 1.63 hrs with BIS, respectively.

There were concerns of increased myocardial ischaemia, infarction, or death due to early extubation after cardiac surgery but research into fast-track protocols have not supported these concerns. On the contrary, they have suggested better cardiac and respiratory outcomes with fast-track techniques [1, 2]. This study supports the fast-track protocols and compares two very distinct anaesthetic techniques and analyses the variables with regard to the influence of BIS monitoring on the anaesthetic drug requirements. Reduction in the anaesthetic drugs requirement as propofol 32% and isoflurane 44% with BIS monitoring is a significant finding in this study, but this did not translate into a reduced length of ICU stay and hospital stay. BIS monitoring decreased the consumption of propofol and sevoflurane significantly by 29% and 40% respectively in a cost and recovery analysis of outpatient anaesthesia using EEG-BIS monitoring [2]. The reduced anaesthetic drug requirements during off-pump CABG can be extrapolated to less myocardial depression, less fall in system vascular resistance, reduced arrhythmias and decreased need for inotropic support or vasoconstrictor medications [3, 30, 31]. These are of great importance in patients with poor LV function, in the elderly population, and in high-risk groups. The study has an important limitation, i.e., the number of patients in the study is quite small (60) to test the hypothesis if BIS prevents awareness, though none of the patients experienced awareness during surgery.

The study raises an important question that these cardiac patients get more anaesthesia than necessary when BIS is not monitored. In this era of fast-track-anaesthesia and increased reliance on volatile anaesthetics and propofol, it is important to limit the anaesthetic agent concentration/dose within permissible limits and this can be achieved with the use of the BIS index. Many physicians would prefer to limit the concentration of volatile inhalational anaesthetics because of concern about myocardial depression during off-pump CABG especially during grafting of the distal vessels when haemodynamic instability is common. During that critical period, it would be prudent to provide just enough anaesthetic agent to keep the patient amnesic while limiting the concentration to avoid myocardial depression. BIS monitoring aids OP-CABG in many ways: monitoring depth of anaesthesia, thus prevents the likelihood of awareness, reduces the anaesthetic agent required hence reduces myocardial depression, aids fast-track extubation, and reduces costs of OP-CABG (excluding the cost of electrodes).

CONCLUSION

BIS monitoring reduces the anaesthetic drug requirements, aids fast-track extubation hence reduces the cost of anaesthesia in patients undergoing OP-CABG without risk of awareness. Its routine use is recommended. Larger prospective studies are needed to extrapolate these findings in the elderly and those undergoing high-risk CABG without cardiopulmonary bypass with poor LV function.

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